

FROM POND TO PLATE: EXAMINING THE POTENTIAL OF SPIRULINA AS A SUSTAINABLE FOOD SOURCE

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ABSTRACT

Spirulina are filamentous blue-green microalgae that are multicellular and belong to a couple of distinct genera. There are around 15 species of Spirulina and Arthrospira combined. Because of its prokaryotic structure, bacteriologists believe that it is a bacterium. Proteins (55%–70%), carbohydrates (15%–25%), essential fatty acids (18%), vitamins, minerals, and pigments like carotenes, chlorophyll a, and chlorophyll b make up its chemical makeup and phycocyanin. It has considerably high macro- and micronutrient contents, can be collected and processed with ease, and grows in water. It is gathered from natural water, dried, and used as human food in many African nations. It is a significant source of protein. To increase the qualitative and quantitative productivity of Spirulina biomass, key growth factors have been investigated. This review offers helpful details on Spirulina production method that is commercially feasible. Large-scale production and novel formulas are further required to add a Spirulina-based protein system to regular diets.

KEYWORDS: Spirulina, growth, production, harvesting, nutrition, side effects, properties

INTRODUCTION

Arthrospira platensis also called as spirulina is a non-toxic blue-green cyanobacterium. It is multicellular and filamentous algae. These are photosynthetic organisms which uses photosynthesis to convert solar light energy into chemical energy. These algal species have a simple reproductive structure. There are three types of algae known as cyanobacteria, macroalgae and microalgae and each differ in their specificities (Becker, 2007). Spirulina is known to be the first known photosynthetic prokaryotes. It contains chlorophyll so as classified into the microalgae group and as bacterium since it is prokaryotic in nature. Microalgal biotechnology refers to the process of producing carotenoids, fatty acids, lipids and phycocyanin for use in health foods and medications, food supplements, fuel production, medications, and cosmetics. Among the major microalgal groups, cyanobacterium is cultivated largely due to its protein content (Soni, 2017).

Spirulina belongs to family monera, class Cyanophceae and family Spirulinaceae. The three well known species of this family are *Arthrospira platensis*, *A. maxima* and *A. fusiformis*. These are rich in nutrition and pharmacological activities. The *S. plantesis* species is the most widespread and widely employed in several industries, particularly the food industry and medicine. Spirulina contains mostly probiotics, antioxidants, nutraceuticals and phytonutrients. Spirulina has been suggested by the United Nations Organization (UNO) as the perfect meal for humanity, and the World Health Organization (WHO) has also recognized Spirulina to be a safe food with good nutritional content. Also, recent studies focus on its therapeutic benefits including hypercholesterolemia, hyperglycemia, cancer, inflammatory illness, antioxidant, cardiovascular disease and

anti-inflammatory properties (Nirae, 2021). The two major group of Spirulina are *Arthrospira platensis*, *A. maxima*. It is rich in micro and macro nutrients in high quantities. This blue green alga is the primary source of nutrition for humans, animals, and aquatic life. Due to the lack of a cell wall, Spirulina platensis is easily digested. It is a staple of both human and animal diets. It is utilized as a protein and vitamin source in humans and has no negative effects. It contains a lot of phenolic acids, tocopherol, and γ -linoleic acids (Priyanka V. Yamgar, Vikrant M. Dhamak, 2022).

GROWTH PARAMETERS

The growth requirements of *A. platensis* are same as other plants. However, they differ in the efficiency of nutrients usage to produce higher biomass and less water requirements. Some of them are briefed below.

Temperature and pH

The suitable temperature for the growth of Spirulina is 29°C - 35°C. But it can grow between 20°C-37°C provided the required nutrients. Temperature exceeding 35°C can lead to the bleaching of culture and its medium. The changes in atmospheric temperature affects the production of Spirulina production. At night time, the growth rate is zero. There is a serious concern of contamination due to the change in temperature conditions as from warm environment. Another parameter influencing the growth is pH. It determines the solubility of the carbon sources and mineral sources of the culture either directly or indirectly. The optimum range is between 9-11 in which it grows well. However, it differs in the composition of mass cultivation procedures due to the sodium and bicarbonate ions (Priyanka V. Yamgar, Vikrant M. Dhamak, 2022). Also, the direct effect of the pH, protein content and pigments on the Spirulina cultures affects the antioxidant properties. The optimum pH condition ensures that there is no risk of contamination due to the alkaline condition in which other microorganisms doesn't grow. Some factors influence the Spirulina metabolism such as availability of nutrients, toxicity of heavy metals and some range of ionization.

Factors influencing climate

The climatic factor which influences Spirulina growth are temperature. Its growth is inhibited when the temperature exceeds 38°C and the growth is least or nil below 17°C. Also 30% of optimum sunlight is enough for its growth. Its growth is best suitable in light and in night or dark, chemical reactions may take place which can result in synthesis of other proteins.

Light

A. platensis as a photosynthetic bacterium which has the ability to convert the light into chemical energy by a process called photosynthesis. The growth of Spirulina needs light intensity. Since it is cultivated in the open system, the solar radiation and the natural light are the source of it. This parameter depends on the environment, local atmosphere, climate, geographical area and season (Sudhakar, 2012). However, the intensity requirements depend from different organisms. It is known that spirulina can make its own food provided with correct light intensity. Spirulina when provided with low light intensity will yield a culture that is rich in proteins and pigments whereas high light intensities yield the highest growth rate. Therefore, the quality of the light provided, the intensity and duration are essential for its growth.

Production and growth rate:

The production and growth rates of Spirulina are affected by the nutrient and salinity concentration. As it grows well in saline conditions, high salinity is required for its growth. It undergoes a simple process known as cell division and proliferates. However, there are reports suggesting that Spirulina can grow even in lower salinity ratio. Its high yield is observed in large ponds (Habib et al., 2008). Also, the availability of certain nutrients and macromolecules can affect the production of Spirulina.

Starting culture

Spirulina grows well in lakes as it can survive the alkaline conditions where other species find difficult to grow. It doesn't grow when the nutrients are fully taken by them. So, for the mother/starting culture, a fully well grown culture is needed. The Spirulina strain chosen has to contain a significant number of coiled filaments (approximately 25% straight filaments) and at least 1% gamma-linolenic acid (GLA) by dry weight. It can be obtained from two ways – diluting the fresh biomass or from the floating cultures (Pal, 2011). The culture area should be maximum for its efficient growth.

Water quality and Media

Water is an essential resource for any plant to grow. In a similar way, water is an important factor for *A. platensis* growth. It affects the solubility nature of the nutrients in culture medium and it accumulates some of the heavy metals on the way towards its growth. So, there are different medium cultures depending on the water source. The media usually contains urea, bicarbonate ions etc. It contains some ions such as chloride, sodium, sulphate which supports nitrogen supply. When these are present in excess, it leads to toxicity. Spirulina is reported to grow efficiently when urea and nitrate are given in sufficient concentrations. As different media are available, the commonly used media is called zarrouks media (Pragya P. &, 2013).

Agitation and Aeration

The culture needs to be well agitated to provide a homogeneous mixture. It ensures that the carbon dioxide, lighting, and all nutrients to be uniformly distributed. It also prevents from thermal stress created inside. Many agitation technologies have been introduced, including motorized paddles, pumps, air light systems and gravity flow. Aeration is important for good yield and better quality of the culture. This can be done by rotators. Turbulent mixing is required to produce higher biomass (Chisti, 2016). The biomass yield is too low or cannot be achieved when the aeration is not supplied sufficiently.

GROWTH PROCESS

Algae can be grown in closed systems or in open systems like ponds, lakes, or lagoons two key technologies are now being evaluated for the Spirulina may be grown in open ponds and closed photobioreactors (PBR). Commercially, both methods are employed to create high-quality items (Singh and Sharma et al.,2012)

Open ponds can be divided into natural bodies of water such lakes, lagoons, ponds, and ponds, as well as constructed ponds or containers. The most popular systems are shallow large systems such as pools, tanks, raceway ponds, and circular ponds. Open systems are simpler to build and operate, which leads to lower manufacturing and operational costs (C.U ugwu et al., 2008). Poor cell light utilisation, evaporative losses, transfer of carbon dioxide to the environment, and the need for additional lighting are among the main drawbacks of open ponds. vast amounts of land. Additionally, open cultivation methods' poor mass transfer rates, which result in lower biomass output, are caused by ineffective aeration. Location, season, temperature, pH level, nutrient availability, and carbon dioxide supply are other factors that affect growth (Cuaresma et al.,2011).

An enclosed, lighted culture tank intended for managed biomass generation might be referred to as a photobioreactor. Photobioreactors are closed systems with no access to the outside environment. Direct contamination and gas exchange with the environment. The closed system, also known as photobioreactors, is a piece of closed machinery that creates a regulated environment and boosts algal productivity. Photobioreactors provide for improved control of culture conditions, including pH levels, carbon dioxide supply, water supply, ideal temperature, effective light intensity, culture density, and culture density. Algal culture systems may be lit by artificial, natural, or a combination of the two. Open ponds are one type of naturally lighted algal production system with a sizable illumination surface area. (Hase et al.,2000). Some difference between open and closed system is given below.

Factors	Open systems (raceway ponds)	Closed systems (photobioreactors)
Space required	High	Low
Area/volume ratio	Low (5–10 m ⁻¹)	High (20–200 m ⁻¹)
Evaporation	High	No evaporation
Water loss	Very high	Low
CO ₂ -loss	High	Low
Temperature	Highly variable	Required cooling
Weather dependence	High	Low
Process control	Difficult	Easy
Shear	Low	High
Cleaning	None	Required
Algal species	Restricted	Flexible
Biomass quality	Variable	Reproducible
Population density	Low	High
Harvesting efficiency	Low	High
Harvesting cost	High	Lower
Light utilization efficiency	Poor	Good
Most costly parameters	Mixing	Oxygen and temperature control
Contamination control	Difficult	Easy
Capital investments	Low	High
Productivity	Low	3–5 times more productive
Hydrodynamic stress on algae	Very low	Low–high
Gas transfer control	Low	High

Table 1: Difference between open and closed system (Cuellar-Bermudez et al.,2015)

Photobioreactors reduce pollution and enable hygienic monoculture growth of algae. The parameters, such as pH, temperature, light intensity, carbon dioxide content, etc., may be better controlled in photobioreactors. Carbon dioxide loss is decreased in photobioreactors. Photobioreactors stop water from evaporating. Higher cell concentrations are possible using photobioreactors. Complex biopharmaceutical synthesis is improved by photobioreactors. The cultivation of many microalgal species is permitted by PBR. PBR design offers quick mass transfer of carbon dioxide and oxygen as well as homogeneous lighting over the culture surface (sharma et al., 2012).

BAGS OF POLYMER

This technology may be used to provide larger production levels, the lowest capital and operational costs, increased biomass density, better climatically regulated conditions, and industrial scalability. Multi-compartment, thin, floating photobioreactors (PBR) can be deployed in any body of water, including salt water ponds, ditches, or on land. The bag floats because the water within it has a lower density than the liquid it is submerged in. Different methods of controlling density enable the bags to be vertical to ease harvesting. Poly Bags float in a cushion of water and provide high productivity outcomes with appropriate light exposure (Licamele et al., 2011).

HARVESTING PROCESS

Always early morning is the optimum time to harvest spirulina because of certain reasons, Spirulina contains a higher percentage of proteins in the morning, Work is made simpler by a cool environment and there will be more opportunities to dry the stuff in the sun (Cuellar-Bermudez et al.,2015). There are main 5 principles to harvest: Filtration and cleaning, Pre-concentration,Neutralization,Disintegration and Dehydration by spray-drying and certain techniques they include (Bharathiraja et al.,2015)

Screening

The use of a fixed filter is thought to be a more effective method of spirulina harvesting, vibrating screens filter the same amount of material per unit of time as inclined screens.They frequently have very high harvesting efficiency. A vibrating screen and an inclined filter are used together. Repeated harvesting causes the culture to become increasingly enriched with Spirulina short filaments or unicellular microalgae that can readily slide through the screen. According to the research, vibrating method may not be the best method for harvesting spirulina on a wide scale.The washing of extra salt from the biomass is required . Frequently, the cleansed cake is homogenised prior after drying (Bharathiraja et al.,2015).

Centrifugation

To remove Spirulina algae from the medium, use centrifugation. Chemical precipitation and centrifugation are both economically viable, with centrifugation being much superior centrifuge is a piece of machinery with a motor that spins something around on a fixed axis while exerting force perpendicular to it. Although this technique is comparatively effective, pelleting delicate algae cells up against the rotor wall runs the risk of harming them. Centrifugation and drying are now regarded as being too expensive for personal usage (Ogbonna et al.,2015). Screening and centrifugation are two basic method for harvesting spirulina after this we dry ,grind and pack them according to our use .

Drying

Sun drying, freeze drying, spray drying, drum drying, and simmering are a few different drying techniques. Sun drying is sufficient to sterilise the algae and make it suitable for consumption because spirulina has a thin, weak cell wall. The drying process shouldn't take less than 2 hours in total. Since the material is exposed to the open air during solar drying, the efficiency is estimated to be approximately 50%, but during vacuum drying, the efficiency can reach up to 80%. The amount of planted and harvested biomass required to produce 1 kg of dried material varies depending on the ultimate moisture content that may be obtained, specifically 4% and 2.5% for sun and vacuum drying, respectively (Papadaki et al.,2017).

Grinding

You may immediately grind spirulina into an ultra-fine powder. Additionally, the aquaculture, aquarium, and poultry sectors utilise it as a feed additive. The most common form of commercial spirulina offered is a dark green powder or a tablet. It is a component of packaged drinks and snacks that are healthy. The paste made from strained spirulina algae is spread out and given three washes in potable water to remove salt before being dried and turned into powder. Using a high impact ultrafine grinding mill, the dried Spirulina flakes are crushed. Approximately 6–10 hours of grinding are required to obtain an average powder size of 200–800 nm. (Papadaki et al.,2017).

Packaging

For better performance and acceptability, spirulina powder is compressed into a tablet or granule shape. According to (Slade et al.,2013), it is designed as a perfectly balanced diet that promotes optimum development and health. For increased stability, biological availability, and general human health, it incorporates proteinate trace minerals.

Dosage preparation

Numerous spirulina dosages have been utilised, however there is not enough evidence to suggest one but in the study. For instance, dosages of 1 to 8 grammes per day for four to six months have been employed in research looking at the advantages of spirulina for high cholesterol. Spirulina blue green algae was given daily for six weeks at a dose of 4.5 grammes to evaluate its impact on hypertension. In a different trial, people with type 2 diabetes were given a supplement containing 1 gramme of spirulina twice day for two months. Your age, gender, and medical history are just a few examples of the variables that might affect the dosage that is right for you (Yamgar PV et al., 2022).

BENEFITS OF SPIRULINA

Nutrition composition

Food is essential for the body to receive essential nutrients. When our bodies cannot synthesize enough nutrients, taking them through our diet is important. In this context, Spirulina is consumed for its high nutrition and good health benefits for decades. It is considered as a powerful, potent and secret food which grows in a natural ecosystem. It comprises of all the nutrients and components in a complete diet. The composition is comprised of macromolecules such as carbohydrates, proteins, fatty acids and essential vitamins, minerals and pigments. There are a class of algae which are easier to consume. Some of them are described below.

Carbohydrates

A. platensis comprises 15-25% of the weight. The well-known carbohydrates are glucose, sucrose and fructose which are present in low amount. Among all, mesoinositol phosphate is a source of inositol and phosphorous that occur in adequate quantities. The medium in which the culture grows has effect on the amount of carbohydrates present and varies depending on it. The important role of spirulina polysaccharides has a wide effect of stimulating the DNA repair mechanism. The carbohydrates of spirulina lack cellulose rather, they are composed of a variety of sugars such as glucose, galactose, mannose, and xylose along with glycogen. This results in easy digestion and nutrient dense which can be consumed by elderly people who have intestinal mal-absorption (Nawal K. Z. AlFadhly, 2022).

Proteins

Spirulina is one of the richest sources of proteins. It constitutes 55%-70% of the weight (Balasubramani et al., 2016). A study suggested that Spirulina can replace 40% of other protein diet. The protein sources of vegetables such as soya flour contains only half of the level as 35% protein content. However, the content may vary in the time of harvesting in daylight. It is considered as the complete protein as it contains all the essential amino acids. It constitutes about 47% of the overall protein content. These amino acids in spirulina are very high making it a protein rich source.

Essential fatty acids

The essential fatty acids intake has a direct influence on cellular activity and the immune system. They are classified as omega-3 and omega-6 fatty acids. These can be converted into simple derivatives in humans. *A. maxima* contains only 10-20% of gamma-linolenic acids whereas *A. platensis* contains 40% of it. So, it represents the best source of this acid. Other fatty acids are present such as stearidonic acid, arachidonic acid and linolenic acid. The recent research is on the sulfolipids present in Spirulina. Thus, this algal species is recommended as the potent food supplement for the deficiency of essential fatty acids (Falquet, 2017).

Vitamins and minerals

Spirulina contains β -carotene, vitamin B1, B2, E, B12 which are naturally found in this. It comprises of 80% of carotenoids which is present in Spirulina. Also, carotenoids have a wide range of effects some types of cancer. The vitamin B12 (cobalamin) is difficult to obtain from vegetarian foods as no vegetables, grains, pulses and fruit contain this. Its deficiency may lead to specific pathological conditions such as HIV infections results in AIDS. It is an important source of vitamin E compared to other grains (Yin, 2017). It also contains vitamin C and D which makes it vitamin rich supplement. Spirulina contains rich mineral ions such as calcium, magnesium, phosphorous, iron. Iron is mostly present in animal foods. Its deficiencies lead to many problems such as anemia. So, it became important source for vegetarians, teenagers and pregnant women (Roberto, 2015).

HEALTH BENEFITS

Anti-inflammation and Antioxidant activities

Spirulina contains many active ingredients and a richest source of phycocyanin, β -carotene which has high content of anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. The phycocyanin activity was obtained after several studies. Spirulina supplementation also increased blood antioxidant levels, with stronger advantages on the redox state and helps athletes. Beta-carotene, alpha-tocopherol, phenol, fatty acid molecules, and a recently identified complex called calcium spirulina are some of the components in the mixture. According to reports, the phytochemical phycocyanin is important for protecting the liver, kidneys, and other organs. Alpha- and beta-carotene, xanthophyll, cryptoxanthin, echinenone, zeaxanthin, and lutein are all found in spirulina's carotenoid which plays important role in antioxidant and anti-inflammatory property. Thus, antioxidants and other nutrients have many health benefits (Ravi et al., 2010).

Free radical scavenging property

It contains a range of components which are capable of free-radical scavenging property. Free radicals are extremely reactive chemical entities having a single unpaired electron. Oxygen and other reactive oxygen species are the most important free radicals which damages the biological system which are the byproducts of aerobic organisms. Reactive Oxygen Species, such as alkoxyl, hydroxyl, peroxy, and superoxide's, are waste products produced in the cells of aerobic organisms. Under typical conditions, the mitochondrial manganese (Mn) superoxide dismutase detoxifies the superoxide anion as part of the natural antioxidant defense mechanisms. Spirulina extracts are high in antioxidants such as carotenoids, glycolipids, phycocyanin, superoxide dismutase, sulfolipids, DNA and RNA which can bind to free radicals and render them harmless. Due to the open chain tetraphyllores structure, phycocyanin is the most effective free radical scavenger (Nirae, 2021).

Anti-viral properties

Spirulina has highest potential in disease resistance. The antiviral functions are due to the nutrients present in the spirulina. The antiviral property is from the dried biomass and water extracts of the spirulina culture. Thus, the antiviral property of Spirulina is from the polysaccharides and other related compounds (Capelli, 2018). Spirulina has excellent promise in many of the connected areas of disease resistance, according to study. Once more, certain elements present in spirulina are crucial to its ability to act as an antiviral. Researchers in Japan isolated a sulfated polysaccharide found in Spirulina to research as an antiviral agent and which was called as 'Calcium Spirulan.' Calcium Spirulan is effective against a variety of viruses. Calcium Spirulan inhibited the replication of enveloped viruses such as Herpes simplex type 1, human cytomegalovirus, measles, mumps, influenza A and HIV-1. The polysaccharide component of Spirulina (similar to Calcium Spirulan) and the remaining components of Spirulina extract after the polysaccharides have been removed both show antiviral properties. Spirulina's anti-viral properties are not only derived from its polysaccharides; other components in Spirulina also play a role in its antiviral activity (Gerald R. Cysewski, 2018).

Anti-cancer property

Spirulina is known to possess anti-cancer properties. The steps of carcinogen are either reversed or inhibited by certain agents prior to the beginning of cancer. The endonuclease activity, which can be enhanced by Spirulina's specific polysaccharide composition, is responsible for the DNA repair mechanism. In addition to it, *A. plantensis* can produce C-phycocyanin, which is a selective inhibitor of cancer genes (Mozafari, 2013). In the past six years, studies on phycocyanin's antitumoral effects have been done. The outcomes have been quite encouraging: A 49% reduction in leukemia cell growth lines and 50% less hepatocellular carcinoma (liver cancer) cell line growth. Inhibition of HeLa cell reproduction; significant reduction in HeLa cells in vitro compared to control cells; induction of apoptotic features, including cell shrinkage in these same HeLa cells; significant reduction in HeLa cells in vitro compared to control cells; impedance of HeLa cell reproduction; and in combination with selenium, phycocyanin was found to be a potent antiproliferative agent against human melanoma cells and human breast adenocarcinoma. (Chen T, 2015)

Metalloprotection property

Spirulina has metalloprotective properties against heavy metals as Cd, lead, mercury, and arsenic. Such heavy metals can have an effect on cellular growth, productivity, and toxicity, which eventually results in cellular death. Furthermore, heavy metals inhibit DNA synthesis. *A. plantensis* increases DNA synthesis and repair while removing heavy metals via a variety of methods including adsorption, enzymatic synthesis, and the formation of extracellular polymers (Romay, 2003).

Pharmaceutical applications of Spirulina

A. platensis is a complete food which is rich in proteins, vitamins, minerals, phycocyanin, chlorophyll, beta carotene and enzymes. The nutraceutical application of spirulina helps in good diet and helps in the prevention of diseases. When the demand for food and nutraceutical supplements are high, organisms which can produce nutritional food or compounds are in high demand as an alternative approach. The applications such as anti-cancer, anti-viral, health potential of Spirulina seeks the importance and necessity of the pharmaceutical as well as nutraceutical properties. Some of the health benefits includes reducing depression, improvement in memory and mental health, reduction in stress, diabetes prevention, enhances immune system, decreases the cholesterol levels, promotes anti-infection property, lower risks in cardiac diseases and as anti-inflammatory agents. As mentioned as superfood by the health professionals, Spirulina acts as a supplement which can prevent aging and prevent against viruses. In developing countries, it plays a more significant role against malnutrition. Spirulina programmes are developed by some important organizations and individuals to address the status of malnutrition. It has been reported that with the supplements of spirulina products, the global rate of malnutrition has been decreased or minimized to 20% (Aloni, 2016).

IMPORTANCE OF SPIRULINA

Spirulina provides benefits that no other creature can compete in today's world, and it has many applications ranging from food to medicine. Due to its nutritional composition, it is regarded as a wonder drug. It boosts immunity and has resistant factors against various infections. It is also widely known for its antioxidant and anticancer properties. It also plays a vital role in diseases such as diabetes, anaemia, hypertension and others due to its multi beneficial effects. It serves as an essential natural product with the potential ability to produce biofuels due to its high lipids and fatty acids content. The therapeutic approaches of spirulina acts as an important dietary nutritional product and inhibits the formation of cytokine by its anti-inflammatory effect (CM et al., 2009). The higher contents of macromolecules make it as a bioactive compound which has a potent role in stimulating the immune levels and in the production of certain cytokines and potential antibodies (Blinkova LP. et al., 2001). Its health benefits include body weight loss, radiation sickness treatment, liver purification, reducing the blood cholesterol levels, generation of new blood cells and detoxification process.

POSSIBLE SIDE EFFECTS

Spirulina should not be consumed by anyone who are allergic to shellfish, seaweed, or other sea vegetables having gout, an autoimmune illness, and a thyroid problem. Spirulina might not be recommended for those who have kidney stones, phenylketonuria, or who are pregnant or breastfeeding. It's likely that spirulina cultivated in the wild can take up contaminants, heavy metals, and microcystins from the water, which are known to cause serious liver damage. Headache, Muscle pain, Sweating, Trouble in sleeping is also found to be some effects (Kannan et al.,2014).

CONCLUSION

The consumption of natural food is limited in the present world which can lead to deficiency of essential nutrients in humans. Their role in disease prevention increases its need worldwide as it possesses less side effects. *S. platensis*, a blue-green algae is produced and is a substitute for other feed and food additives due to its high protein, pigments, polyunsaturated fatty acid (linolenic acid), enzyme, vitamins and mineral content. It is traditionally used in some parts of the Indian subcontinent for its therapeutic roles. This paper focuses on the different growth parameters, cultivation systems, climatic conditions in which spirulina can grow, some of the harvesting systems in detail and the production processes. It presents the different methods for its growth to significantly increase the production and yield a high biomass with all the nutrients.

The pharmacological properties of spirulina which includes anticancer, antiviral, antibacterial, metalloprotective, antioxidant, and immunostimulant properties. Other properties include anti-aging and drug delivery. Spirulina's anticancer, antiviral, and antimicrobial effects are due to its endonuclease contents (repairing damaged DNA), calcium sulfated polysaccharide (which blocks in vitro virus replication), and fatty acids (linolenic acid). the presence of beta-carotene, selenium, vitamin C, vitamin D are related to the metalloprotective role. *S. platensis* is a mixture of potential antioxidants and its pigments are related to the health benefits. It includes chlorophyll, carotenoids and phycocyanin. Therefore, this review focuses on the growth requirements and the nutritional aspects of Spirulina.

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